

ELECTRICAL BEHAVIOR OF A CFRP UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATE UNDER TEMPERATURE VARIATION

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1 Introduction

Electrical resistance change method (ERCM) has been an area of interest as a sensing system for CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic) structures. It utilizes an electrical network of conductive carbon fibers, which can serve as a distributed sensor by properly locating electrodes on surface of a structure. For example, the electrical resistance changes due to structural deformation enable strain monitoring [1,2], and those due to interruption in the electric current flow allow structural damage detection [3,4].

The main advantage of ERCM over other health monitoring methods is that ERCM can be simply applied to existing CFRP structures without major structural modification or additional expensive equipment. Optical fiber sensors [5] is one of the promising structural health monitoring systems, which have shown great sensitivity for deformation and damage, but it might degrade the structural strength due to embedding the optical fibers [6]. Piezoelectric sensors [7] are also applicable, but requires more complicated set up and data analysis than ERCM.

In addition, the ERCM may be combined with a thermally mendable polymer as the matrix, thereby allowing the damage to be healed using resistive heating of carbon fibers. High electrical conductivity of carbon fibers can be utilized as a heat source by applying large amounts of electrical currents. A polymer which has thermally mendable properties has been synthesized by Chen et al. [8], and the researchers in the same group have synthesized a series of thermally mendable polymers. It has been shown that thermally mendable polymers can be applied as matrix [9] of a CFRP laminate. The electrical network of CFRP laminates enables self-heating as well as self-sensing using the same system of electrodes. Therefore, subcritical damage occurred in a composite with a thermally mendable

polymer matrix can be both detected and repaired electrically.

Applying the ERCM to existing structures requires a relationship between electrical resistance changes and changes in a structural state. The influences of deformation and damage occurrence on electrical resistance changes are well characterized, but they are usually assumed under constant temperature. The electrical resistance is strongly affected by ambient temperature [10,11], but there has been fewer numbers of investigations. The difficulty in characterizing temperature effect on electrical resistance is that elevated temperature of a CFRP laminate causes both changes in electrical resistivity of carbon fibers and thermal expansion of matrix resin. Elevated temperature decreases electrical resistance due to property of carbon fibers whereas corresponding thermal expansion increases it. Furthermore, anisotropic property of a CFRP laminate has to be also considered for electrical resistance, meaning that fiber direction and other directions have different electrical conductivities. Due to this anisotropy, paths of electrical currents vary depending on electrodes location, resulting in different sensitivities.

In this paper, the dependence of the electrical resistance on temperature is first investigated in terms of the anisotropic properties of a unidirectional CFRP laminate. The electric resistances in the fiber direction and transverse direction are measured with elevated temperature using different location of electrodes. Next, the same laminate is heated again under constraint of thermal expansion in order to separate the influences of change in electrical resistivity from one from thermal expansion. A tensile test is also conducted to establish a constitutive relationship between electrical resistance, temperature change and mechanical strain.

2 Thermal Influences on Electrical Resistance

2.1 Electrical Anisotropy

Electrical resistance change of a unidirectional CFRP laminate can be represented by electrical resistivity ρ , and geometry with length l and cross section area A as other conductive materials.

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \frac{\Delta \rho}{\rho_0} + \frac{\Delta l}{l_0} - \frac{\Delta A}{A_0} \quad (1)$$

Subscript 0 represents initial values. Under steady ambient condition with constant temperature and humidity, fraction of the electrical resistance change $\Delta r = \Delta R/R_0$ increases proportionally to the nominal strain ε with a coefficient η , which is called a gauge factor. When temperature also changes, fraction of the electrical resistance change decreases due to temperature dependence of electrical resistivity, as shown in Eq. (2).

$$\Delta r = \alpha_\rho \Delta T + \eta \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Here, the fraction of electrical resistivity is replaced by temperature coefficient of resistivity α_ρ .

$$\frac{\Delta \rho}{\rho_0} = \alpha_\rho \Delta T \quad (3)$$

Under a loading condition with varied temperature, the nominal strain ε can be separated into thermal strain and strain caused by external forces ε_M .

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_M + \alpha_\varepsilon \Delta T \quad (4)$$

Here, coefficient of thermal expansion is denoted as α_ε . Substituting Eq. (4) into Eq. (2), the fraction of electrical resistance change can be expressed by a temperature related term and an external forces related term.

$$\Delta r = (\alpha_\rho + \eta \alpha_\varepsilon) \Delta T + \eta \varepsilon_M \quad (5)$$

Since a CFRP laminate is composed of conductive carbon fibers and insulated polymer matrix, electrical currents mainly flow along fiber direction. Transverse direction is also conductive by forming conducting paths through contacts between neighboring carbon fibers, but the conductivity is about 1/1000 of one in fiber direction [12]. Therefore, electrical conductivity of a unidirectional

CFRP laminate is regarded as orthotropic along carbon fibers, as shown in Fig. 1 (a). Eq. (5) is actually expressed as the following matrix form with superscripts L and T representing fiber direction and transverse direction, respectively.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Delta r^L \\ \Delta r^T \end{pmatrix} = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_\rho^L \\ \alpha_\rho^T \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \eta^L & \eta^{LT} \\ \eta^{TL} & \eta^T \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_\varepsilon^L \\ \alpha_\varepsilon^T \end{pmatrix} \right\} \Delta T + \begin{pmatrix} \eta^L & \eta^{LT} \\ \eta^{TL} & \eta^T \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_M^L \\ \varepsilon_M^T \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Since the coefficient of thermal expansion in the fiber direction is much smaller than one in the transverse direction, the fraction of electrical resistance in each direction is expressed by neglecting the coefficient of thermal expansion in the fiber direction, $\alpha_\varepsilon^L = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta r^L &= (\alpha_\rho^L + \eta^{LT} \alpha_\varepsilon^T) \Delta T + \eta^L \varepsilon_M^L + \eta^{LT} \varepsilon_M^T \\ \Delta r^T &= (\alpha_\rho^T + \eta^T \alpha_\varepsilon^T) \Delta T + \eta^{TL} \varepsilon_M^L + \eta^T \varepsilon_M^T \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

When no external forces are applied to a CFRP laminate, each electrical resistance changes in accordance with corresponding temperature coefficient of resistivity and thermal expansion of matrix.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta r^L &= (\alpha_\rho^L + \eta^{LT} \alpha_\varepsilon^T) \Delta T \\ \Delta r^T &= (\alpha_\rho^T + \eta^T \alpha_\varepsilon^T) \Delta T \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It is known that carbon fibers have negative temperature coefficient of resistivity as it is typical for semiconducting materials, meaning that elevated temperature decreases the electrical resistance. On the other hand, thermal expansion of polymer may decrease contacts between neighboring carbon fibers, which are paths of electrical currents as shown in Fig. 1 (b), resulting in the resistivity increase. These effects should be simultaneously considered and separately evaluated for applying ERCM to existing structures.

2.2 Experiment

Electrical resistance changes with elevated temperature are measured in the fiber direction and the transverse direction. An unidirectional CFRP

Fig. 1 Electrical current flow in a unidirectional CFRP laminate (a), and influence of thermal expansion (b)

laminates $[0_8]_T$ is made of PYROFIL #380 G250 prepreg produced by Mitsubishi Layon Co Ltd. Thickness of the laminate is 2.5 mm. Size of the specimen is 50 mm \times 20 mm cut from the laminate, and then silver paint is painted on it.

Two kinds of specimens regarding electrode locations are prepared to evaluate orthotropic electrical property. One has the electrodes located on side surfaces for electrical current input, and the electrodes encircling the laminate with 5.0 mm width for potential difference measurement. The electrodes are located either in fiber direction or transverse direction as shown in Fig. 2 (a) and (b), respectively. The electrical resistance measured in this manner is called volume resistance, whose electrical current uniformly distributes inside the laminate (Fig. 4 (a)). The other has all electrodes for both electrical current input and potential difference measurement only on top surface as shown in Fig. 3 (a) and (b) for fiber direction and transverse direction, respectively. Top electrodes are more feasible for applying the ERCM to structures, but cause more complex distribution of electrical currents as high electrical density near top surface, gradually decreasing to bottom surface as described in Fig. 4 (b). The electrical resistance obtained from top electrodes is called surface resistance.

Conducting wires are attached on the electrodes by the same silver paint, covered by epoxy adhesive for protection. The specimens are gradually heated on a hotplate at the constant rate from the room temperature to 50 °C. The electrical resistances and the temperature are measured using a KEITHLEY 2750 multimeter and a thermocouple at every second. After measuring the electrical resistance with elevated temperature, another laminate is attached below in the perpendicular direction as shown in Fig. 5. All four specimens shown in Fig. 2 (a)(b) and Fig. 3 (a)(b) are constrained in the same way, and their electrical resistances are measured again on a hotplate. Since small coefficient of carbon fibers constrains the thermal expansion of matrix resin, the electrical resistance change becomes different from initial behavior even at the same temperature. Two pairs of $\Delta r^i/\Delta T$ ($i = L$ and T) and α_ε^T obtained in initial state and constraint state give a solution of α_ρ^L and η^{LT} in the fiber direction, and α_ρ^T and η^T in the transverse direction shown in Eq. (8), respectively. To confirm the effect of constraint, thermal strain is also measured using other specimens with two marks on the surface, whose distance is measured by a digital image extensometer as shown in Fig. 6. The remaining coefficients in Eq. (7) are η^L for the fiber direction and η^{TL} for the transverse direction. Since only one coefficient is unknown in each direction, a tensile test with an electrical resistance measurement is conducted under constant temperature. Nominal strains in fiber and transverse directions can be expressed by poisson's ratios ν^{JT} and ν^{TL} , and Eq. (7) is expressed as below under constant temperature.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta r^L &= (\eta^L - \eta^{LT} \nu^{LT}) \varepsilon_M^L \\ \Delta r^T &= (-\nu^{TL} \eta^{TL} + \eta^T) \varepsilon_M^T \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

One specimen is prepared as its longitudinal directions orient along fiber direction, and the other specimen is perpendicular to it. The specimens are prepared from the same laminate as used in the external heating test. Dimension of the specimens is shown in Fig. 7, with GFRP tabs are attached for cramping. Two kinds of electrode locations are also prepared as one specimen has four electrodes with 5.0 mm width encircling the laminate, and the other has them only on top surface. Mechanical strain is measured at a crosshead speed of 1.0 mm/min.

Fig. 2 Specimen for measuring volume resistance in fiber direction (a) and transverse direction (b)

Fig. 3 Specimen for measuring surface resistance in fiber direction (a) and transverse direction (b)

Fig. 4 Paths of electrical currents formed in volume resistance (a) and surface resistance (b)

Fig. 5 Specimen configuration for constraining thermal expansion by perpendicularly adhering another laminate

Fig. 6 Measurement of thermal expansion by a digital image extensometer

Figure 7 Specimen dimensions for a tensile test with measuring volume resistance on top figure and surface resistance on bottom figure

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Electrical Anisotropy

The initial resistance are measured and summarized in Table 1. The fiber direction has about 600 ~ 700 times lower electrical resistance than the transverse direction, as explained in Fig. 1(a). The volume resistance is lower than the surface resistance in both directions due to larger paths of electrical currents, described in Fig. 4. The difference is larger in the fiber direction because the side electrodes can directly utilize carbon fibers as path of electrical currents whereas both locations form paths through contacts between neighboring carbon fibers in the transverse direction.

The electrical resistance changes during heating on a hotplate are shown in Fig. 8. The fraction of electrical resistance change is also the most significant for the volume resistance in the fiber

direction. As the thermal expansion is assumed to be negligible in the fiber direction, the elevated temperature directly affects the semiconducting property of carbon fibers. On the other hand, the paths of electrical currents through the contacts between neighboring carbon fibers decrease due to thermal expansion as explained in Fig. 1 (b), resulting in smaller decrease in the transverse direction. The slope of the electrical resistance change is still negative in Fig. 8, meaning that the semiconducting property of carbon fibers in the transverse direction is more significant than the resistance increase due to thermal expansion. In addition, the surface resistance in the fiber direction shows similar to the results in the transverse direction. The top electrodes only contacts with carbon fibers near surface, and forms paths of electrical currents through contacts between neighboring carbon fibers as described in Fig. 4(b). These paths are similarly formed as they are in the transverse direction, resulting in the similar fraction of electrical resistance change.

Table 1. Initial electrical resistance in fiber and transverse directions

	Fiber		Transverse	
	Volume	Surface	Volume	Surface
Resistance	0.098	0.14	70	80

Fig. 8 Electrical resistance changes with various electrode locations

3.2 Constraint of thermal expansion

The results of thermal strain measurement are shown in Fig. 9. Thermal strain in the fiber direction is almost zero in the temperature range from room temperature to 50 °C as assumed. The transverse direction showed thermal strain 1240 $\mu\epsilon$ when the temperature increase was 20 °C. The CTE can be calculated from linear estimation of this slope, resulting in 62.0 $\mu\epsilon/K$. This value corresponds well to the CTE of epoxy resin that is a matrix of this composite. These results confirmed that the unidirectional CFRP laminate has negligible thermal expansion in the fiber direction and equivalent CTE of matrix resin in the transverse direction.

Next, the same specimen is perpendicularly adhered on another laminate, as shown in Fig. 5. The electrical resistance and the thermal strain are measured in the same way as previous experiments, and the influence of constraint is evaluated. The result of constraint thermal expansion is plotted in Fig. 9. Thermal strain of constraint specimen is not negligible because of thermal expansion of adhesive layer between top and bottom laminate and the thickness of the top panel, but it is much smaller compared to one initially obtained.

Influence of constraint on electrical resistance change is shown in Fig. 10 for volume resistance and Fig. 11 for surface resistance in (a) fiber direction and (b) transverse direction. Dashed lines are results obtained before the constraint, shown in

Fig. 9 Influence of constraint on thermal expansion

Fig. 10 Volume resistance measurements in fiber direction (a) and transverse direction (b) before and after constraint

Fig. 11 Surface resistance measurements in fiber direction (a) and transverse direction (b) before and after constraint

Fig. 8, and solid lines are results after the constraint. All results showed further decrease in electrical resistance due to the constraint. The constraint of bottom laminate keeps the contacts of carbon fibers and causes further decrease in electrical resistance. Influence of constraint seems smaller for surface resistance in the fiber direction (Fig. 11 (a)), but linear estimation still indicates further decrease. It implies that fiber direction also forms paths of electrical currents through contacts between carbon fibers although main paths go along them.

3.3 Tensile Test

To obtain remaining constants η^L and η^{TL} , a tensile test is conducted with electrical resistance measurement. The results are shown in Fig. 12 (a) in the fiber direction and (b) in the transverse direction. Electrical resistances increase under tensile loading except for volume resistance in the fiber direction. Typical conductive materials show higher electrical resistance in longer dimension and smaller cross section. This characteristic applies to carbon fibers,

but as for a CFRP laminate in the fiber direction, smaller cross section may decrease electrical resistance. Number of contacts between neighboring carbon fibers, which forms paths of electrical currents, could increase because of Poisson's effect. In the transverse direction, paths of electrical currents simply decrease due to separation of contacts between neighboring carbon fibers in the longitudinal direction, resulting in increase in electrical resistance.

Fig. 12 Electrical resistance change under tensile loading for volume resistance (a) and surface resistance (b)

3.4 Relationship between electrical resistance, temperature change and mechanical strain

The constants for representing a relationship between electrical resistance, temperature change and mechanical strain can be determined from the experimental results. The slope of linear estimation $\Delta r^i/\Delta T$ ($i = L$ and T) and thermal expansion α_ε^T obtained from initial state and constraint state (Fig. 11 and Fig. 12) are summarized in Table 2, including Poisson's ratio and $\Delta r^i/\varepsilon^M$ obtained in a tensile test. Each experiment was repeated several times and the values in the table are average of the results. The corresponding constants are calculated from Eq. (8) and Eq. (9) and determined in Eq. (10) for volume resistance and Eq. (11) for surface resistance.

Close values of temperature coefficient of resistivity in transvers direction for volume resistance and surface resistance resulted from similar paths of electrical currents that are contacts between neighboring carbon fibers. Temperature coefficient of resistivity in fiber direction for surface resistance is also similar, meaning that electrical resistance is not only affected by property of carbon fibers, but also by contact between neighboring carbon fibers as described in Fig. 4 (b). One in fiber direction for volume resistance is much larger than others because it is significantly affected by the electrical property of carbon fibers.

As for influence of deformation, interaction terms

Table 2 Summary of experimentally obtained values required for determining constants

	Initial state		Constraint state	
	Fiber	Transverse	Fiber	Tarnsverse
α_ε	0	62.6	0	37.3
$\Delta r^i/\Delta T_V$	-1850	-651	-2080	-682
$\Delta r^i/\Delta T_S$	-610	-656	-662	-698
ν	0.404	0.0214	-	-
$\Delta r^i/\varepsilon^M_V$	-1.96	1.46	-	-
$\Delta r^i/\varepsilon^M_S$	1.33	1.78		

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{\rho}^L \\ \alpha_{\rho}^T \end{pmatrix}_V = \begin{pmatrix} -2460 \\ -728 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \eta^L & \eta^{LT} \\ \eta^{TL} & \eta^T \end{pmatrix}_V = \begin{pmatrix} 1.57 & 8.75 \\ -10.4 & 1.24 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{\rho}^L \\ \alpha_{\rho}^T \end{pmatrix}_S = \begin{pmatrix} -751 \\ -760 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \eta^L & \eta^{LT} \\ \eta^{TL} & \eta^T \end{pmatrix}_S = \begin{pmatrix} 2.16 & 2.06 \\ -5.40 & 1.66 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

η^{LT} and η^{TL} are bigger than direct terms η^L and η^T for volume resistance, causing decrease in electrical resistance under tensile loading. Interaction terms become smaller for surface resistance, but direct terms are similar to each other. These results indicate that the larger area for electrical current input forms the more paths of electrical current through carbon fiber contacts. It means the gauge factors could be controlled by area of electrodes, but further investigation is required to verify it.

4 Conclusions

This paper established a relationship between electrical resistance, temperature change and deformation of unidirectional CFRP laminate. Anisotropic characteristics of electrical resistance were investigated in the fiber direction and transverse direction. Different electrode locations were also investigated by placing electrodes on all surfaces encircling the laminate for volume resistance or only on top surface for surface resistance.

First, thermal influences on electrical resistance were separated into resistivity change of carbon fibers and expansion of polymer, and they were quantitatively evaluated from the measurements of electrical resistance on a hotplate. Constraint of thermal expansion by perpendicularly attaching another laminate resulted in further decrease in electrical resistance and enabled to derive coefficients for thermal influences. Volume resistance showed a large coefficient of resistivity in fiber direction due to property of a carbon fiber. On

the other hand, surface resistance in fiber direction resulted in a smaller coefficient of resistivity, which is similar to those in transverse direction, meaning that they are affected by paths of electrical currents formed through contacts between neighboring carbon fibers.

Second, a tensile test was conducted to obtain remaining coefficients for mechanical strain. It was found that direct terms are similar in both directions regardless of electrode locations. However, interaction terms generated due to Poisson's effect were more significant than direct terms, particularly for volume resistance, causing decrease in volume resistance. These quantitative relationships of electrical resistance changes can be usefully used for sensing system of CFRP structures.

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